

A Simple Identity Highlighting Additivity in Higher-Order Derivatives of Polynomial Functions

Joel Naithik Salivendra
Alphores Junior College, India

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Abstract

This paper presents a simple identity involving the $(n - 1)$ th derivative of degree- n polynomial functions that omit the x^{n-1} term. It is shown that the resulting derivative is a linear function that satisfies the property $f(x_1 + x_2) = f(x_1) + f(x_2)$, i.e., it is additive over its inputs. This result offers a clean and elegant example of the linearity inherent in higher-order derivatives and provides insight into the structure of polynomial differentiation.

1. Introduction

While testing the limits of function evaluation, I started wondering how far the idea of additivity—specifically the identity $f(x_1 + x_2) = f(x_1) + f(x_2)$ —would hold for different types of functions.

I decided to try this with polynomial functions. What I noticed was that additivity tends to break down more and more as the constant term increases, or as the degree of the polynomial gets higher. Eventually, I realized that this property only holds perfectly for a linear monomial function like $f(x) = kx$.

So I thought: if additivity only works for linear monomials, then maybe the way to make a higher-degree polynomial behave that way is to remove the constant term and reduce its degree—basically, by differentiating it enough times. That's what led me to try differentiating a general polynomial, and in the process, I came across a simple but interesting identity.

2. Main Result

Let

$$f(x) = ax^n + bx^{n-2} + cx^{n-3} + \dots + k$$

be a degree- n polynomial that does not contain the term x^{n-1} . Then, the $(n - 1)$ th derivative of $f(x)$, denoted $f^{(n-1)}(x)$, satisfies the identity:

$$f^{(n-1)}(x_1 + x_2) = f^{(n-1)}(x_1) + f^{(n-1)}(x_2).$$

3. Proof

Let us consider a polynomial function of the form:

$$f(x) = ax^n + bx^{n-2} + cx^{n-3} + \dots + kx^{n-n},$$

which notably omits the x^{n-1} term.

Differentiating $f(x)$ once:

$$f^{(1)}(x) = nax^{n-1} + (n-2)bx^{n-3} + (n-3)cx^{n-4} + \dots$$

Differentiating again:

$$f^{(2)}(x) = n(n-1)ax^{n-2} + (n-2)(n-3)bx^{n-4} + \dots$$

Continuing this process, we differentiate $f(x)$ a total of $(n-1)$ times. All terms with degree lower than $n-1$ vanish, and we are left with:

$$f^{(n-1)}(x) = n! \cdot a \cdot x.$$

Let $p = n!a$. Then:

$$f^{(n-1)}(x) = px,$$

which is a linear monomial function.

This function satisfies the additivity property:

$$f^{(n-1)}(x_1 + x_2) = p(x_1 + x_2) = px_1 + px_2 = f^{(n-1)}(x_1) + f^{(n-1)}(x_2).$$

Hence, the $(n-1)$ th derivative of such a polynomial is an additive linear function.

4. Examples

Example 1: Polynomial Function of Degree 3

Consider the polynomial function:

$$f(x) = 3x^3 + 4x + 6$$

The first and second derivatives are:

$$f^{(1)}(x) = 9x^2 + 4, \quad f^{(2)}(x) = 18x$$

Now evaluate the second derivative at $x = 5$:

$$f^{(2)}(5) = 18 \cdot 5 = 90$$

Also, evaluate at $x = 2$ and $x = 3$:

$$f^{(2)}(2) + f^{(2)}(3) = 18 \cdot 2 + 18 \cdot 3 = 36 + 54 = 90$$

Thus,

$$f^{(2)}(5) = f^{(2)}(2) + f^{(2)}(3)$$

Example 2: Polynomial Function of Degree 5

Consider the polynomial:

$$f(x) = 4x^5 + 2x^4 + 6x^2 + 3x + 5$$

Its derivatives are:

$$f^{(1)}(x) = 20x^4 + 8x^3 + 12x + 3$$

$$f^{(2)}(x) = 80x^3 + 24x + 12$$

$$f^{(3)}(x) = 240x^2 + 24$$

$$f^{(4)}(x) = 480x$$

Evaluate the fourth derivative at $x = 5$:

$$f^{(4)}(5) = 480 \cdot 5 = 2400$$

Also, evaluate at $x = 2$ and $x = 3$:

$$f^{(4)}(2) + f^{(4)}(3) = 480 \cdot 2 + 480 \cdot 3 = 960 + 1440 = 2400$$

Thus:

$$f^{(4)}(5) = f^{(4)}(2) + f^{(4)}(3)$$

These examples clearly demonstrate the identity:

$$f^{(n-1)}(x_1 + x_2) = f^{(n-1)}(x_1) + f^{(n-1)}(x_2)$$

for suitable polynomial functions and derivative orders.

5. Why Omit the x^{n-1} Term?

Consider a polynomial function:

$$f(x) = ax^n + bx^{n-1} + cx^{n-2} + \dots + k$$

Differentiating $f(x)$ $n - 1$ times:

$$f^{(n-1)}(x) = n!ax + (n - 1)!b$$

Define $p = n!a$ and $q = (n - 1)!b$. Then:

$$f^{(n-1)}(x) = px + q$$

Here, the constant term q breaks the clean additivity property:

$$f^{(n-1)}(x_1 + x_2) = p(x_1 + x_2) + q \neq px_1 + q + px_2 + q = f^{(n-1)}(x_1) + f^{(n-1)}(x_2)$$

Hence, to ensure the additivity identity remains valid, the x^{n-1} term must be omitted to eliminate the constant q .

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we explored what happens when we differentiate an n -degree polynomial multiple times, especially when the x^{n-1} term is left out. We found that if this term is omitted, the $(n - 1)$ th derivative becomes something surprisingly simple: just a multiple of the coefficient of the x^n term.

This led to a nice additive property, something we would not normally expect from arbitrary polynomials. We also looked into why the x^{n-1} term needs to be removed in the first place. It turns out that if it's included, a constant term shows up before the final differentiation, which breaks this clean additivity.

Even though this might seem like a small tweak, it reveals how much the structure of a polynomial affects its behavior when differentiated. This idea might seem basic, but it opens up room to think about how small changes to functions can lead to interesting patterns and results.

In the future, it might be worth looking at whether removing other terms (besides x^{n-1}) causes similar effects—or whether this identity shows up in other types of functions too.

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